
Emotional and Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students in relation to their Mental Health

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ABSTRACT

The primary aim of the study was to examine the correlation between the adjustment of secondary level students and their mental health in the Coochbehar district of West Bengal, India. A descriptive survey research design was used for conducting the present study. For the purpose of the study, a total of eight high schools, including four from urban areas and four from rural areas, were conveniently selected. Additionally, 160 secondary level students (80 boys and 80 girls) were selected using a simple random sampling technique. Data were collected using Mental Health scale developed by Sushma Talesara and Akhtar Bano and the Adjustment Inventory developed by A.K.P. Sinha & R.P. Singh (2005). The researchers applied statistical methods such as Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), t- test and Pearson's Product-moment correlation for the analysis and interpretation of the collected data. The study revealed that most students, regardless of their gender or locality, showed average levels of emotional and educational adjustment. No statistically significant difference was found in emotional adjustment based on gender and locality. Additionally, the study did not find any statistically significant difference in educational adjustment based on gender. However, mean difference was observed between urban students and rural students in terms of educational adjustment. A positive correlation was observed between emotional adjustment and mental health of secondary level students. However a slight negative correlation was found between educational adjustment ability and mental health of students.

Keywords: Adjustment, Emotional Adjustment, Educational Adjustment, Mental Health, Secondary Level Students

1. Introduction

School is a miniature of society and a major socialization institution for any child. Schools provide children with valuable opportunities to develop crucial social skills, enabling them to engage with the broader community and shape their

identities. By spending significant time in schools, students gain essential abilities in social, emotional, and academic realms, contributing significantly to their holistic growth and development (Raju & Rahamtulla, 2007; Frey, Fisher & Smith, 2019). As children begin their school journey, they encounter the challenges of adapting to teachers, academic tasks, and a diverse peer group. Adjustment for secondary level students is a complex process that encompasses various aspects of their lives as they transition from childhood to adolescence. This period, typically spanning from ages 14 to 18, is marked by significant physical, emotional, cognitive, and social changes. Effective adjustment during these formative years is crucial for their overall well-being and future success.

It is common to hear that some individuals have difficulty adapting to new situations or face challenges when trying to adjust to changes in their environment. This leads us to ask: what exactly is adjustment and how does it affect our lives? Adjustment is a vital skill necessary for peaceful living. It involves striking a balance between our needs and what brings us happiness. As human beings, we constantly strive to meet our basic physical needs, such as hunger and protection from harm. At the same time, we seek to fulfil psychological needs, such as emotional security and acceptance. In our pursuit of a fulfilling life in a complex world, we face numerous needs and desires. This leads to an ongoing process of interaction between ourselves and our environment. In this process, we either attempt to adjust and change our surroundings or focus on maintaining our personal environment in an orderly and organized manner (War Nongbri, 2019). Schools and homes play significant roles in teaching us how to adapt to different circumstances. When we adjust well, we can handle challenges more effectively and feel more at ease in our daily lives.

The concept of "adjustment" originates from biology, particularly the idea of organisms adapting to their physical environment to ensure survival. In biological terms, adjustments or adaptations help organisms better fit into their surroundings and increase their chances of thriving. According to Darwin's Theory of Evolution (1859), individuals who successfully adapt to societal changes are the ones who survive, while those who fail to adapt face the risk of extinction. Therefore, the ability to adjust is crucial for individual success. According to Good ((1959) "Adjustment is the process of finding and adopting modes of behaviour suitable to the environment or the changes in the environment". Schneiders (1960) defined adjustment as "... a process, involving both mental and behavioral responses, by which an individual strives to cope successfully with inner needs, tensions, frustrations and conflicts and affect a degree of harmony between inner demands and those imposed on him by the objective world in which he lives". Basically, adjustment is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs. Thus Adjustment influences the achievement and personality development of the students in school. In essence, adjustment in students' school life is vital for creating a positive and supportive educational experience that promotes both academic performance and personal development. Students can experience different types of adjustment. The current study specifically investigates two essential types of student adjustment: emotional and educational adjustments.

1.1 Emotional Adjustment

Emotional adjustment plays a crucial role in people's lives as it directly impacts their overall well-being and quality of relationships. Emotional adjustment refers to the ability to cope with and manage one's feelings in response to changes or challenges in life. It involves adapting emotionally to new situations, experiences, or relationships, in a way that promotes personal well-being and psychological balance. Emotional adjustment involves accepting and adapting to one's circumstances, which can include adjusting attitudes and expressing emotions appropriately based on the situation. It refers to maintaining emotional balance despite internal and external challenges and pressures (Arjun et. al, 2022).

1.2 Educational Adjustment

Educational adjustment refers to the modifications and accommodations made within the educational environment to meet the diverse needs of students, ensuring equitable access to learning opportunities. This process involves adapting teaching strategies, curricula, and assessments to address various learning styles, abilities, and challenges, including those of students with disabilities or special needs. Effective educational adjustments promote inclusivity by providing support such as individualized instruction, assistive technologies, and flexible classroom settings, thereby fostering an environment where all students can thrive academically and socially. These adjustments are crucial for creating a supportive and adaptive learning atmosphere that helps each student reach their full potential.

1.3 Mental Health

The term 'Mental Health' is composed of two words: 'Mental' and 'Health.' 'Health' generally means sound condition or well-being or freedom from diseases. An individual's development is closely related to their health. If a person is not in good health, they may struggle to perform their duties and responsibilities effectively, making personal health a critical priority. Education plays a key role in teaching individuals how to maintain and enhance their health. Its primary goal is to foster a healthy personality, making health education a vital component. Mental health is essential not only in formal educational settings but also in informal environments such as families and communities. **The World Health Organization (WHO)** defines mental health as..... “a condition of overall well-being where each individual achieves their full potential, effectively handles the typical stresses of life, can engage in productive and meaningful work, and contributes positively to their community.’

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Sathia Raj (2023) conducted a comparative analysis of students' mental health and adjustment levels. The study found a significant correlation between the types of families among male respondents in Government school and their adjustment.

Taneja & Wadhwa (2023) conducted a study to examining the correlation between the mental health and adjustment problems of senior secondary school students. The results indicated a negative and significant correlation between mental health and adjustment problems.

D'souza and Tripathi (2022) investigated the mental health and social adjustment of middle school girls from urban and rural areas. The findings revealed a significant disparity in adjustment levels between middle school girls in rural and urban settings. Furthermore, the study identified a noteworthy correlation between the mental health and social adjustment of middle school girls in both rural and urban schools.

Kumar (2021) carried out a survey based study on mental health and adjustment problems of faced by higher secondary students. The findings indicated significant differences in mental health and adjustment problems based on gender, medium of instruction (Tamil or English), academic subject group (arts, science, vocational), type of school (boys', girls', co-education), and the rural or urban setting of higher secondary students. Additionally, a significant negative relationship was observed between the mental health and adjustment problems of these students.

Shinde (2018) did a research work on mental health and adjustment for college students. The study found no significant gender difference concerning the adjustment of adolescents. However, significant gender differences were found in health and educational adjustment. No significant gender differences were found in home, social, and emotional adjustment. There was no significant gender difference in mental health. Additionally, Adjustment was not significantly associated with mental health.

Murgan (2017) studied to examine the correlation between the mental health and adjustment levels of students in higher secondary school. The findings revealed a significant relationship between the mental health and adjustment of higher secondary school students. However, the study found a significant difference in the mental health of male and female higher secondary school students.

Silvy (2017) conducted a study examining the Relationship between Mental Health and Adjustment among 150 adolescent students randomly selected from six Senior Secondary Schools. The study found a positive correlation between the Mental Health and Adjustment of male and female adolescent students, as well as those in the science and humanities groups.

Shokeen (2017) investigated to explore the relationship between mental health and social adjustment of adolescents. The findings revealed a positive significant relationship between the Mental Health and Social Adjustment in the adolescents.

Srinivasan and Senkolemari (2016) carried out a study on the mental health and adjustment levels of prospective secondary education teachers. The findings indicated that the mental health of prospective secondary education teachers was rated as average and good. However, the adjustment levels were found to be very unsatisfactory for males and unsatisfactory for females. The correlation between mental health and adjustment variables was identified as very low and negative.

Singh (2015) conducted a study to explore the importance of the relationship between adjustment, emotional intelligence, and mental health among senior secondary school students. The study found a significant positive correlation between adjustment and both emotional intelligence and mental health.

3. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Adjustment plays a vital role in personal development of every individual. How well an individual adapts to their physical and social surroundings affects their overall well-being. Since our environments are constantly changing, it's important for people to adjust and adapt accordingly. In this way, adjustment involves maintaining a harmonious relationship between individuals and their surroundings, including the people around them (Crow & Crow, 1956). The findings of this study are important for a variety of stakeholders, including educators, parents, policymakers, and mental health professionals. The results could promote better collaboration between parents and schools, influence policies to create more inclusive educational environments, and enhance mental health support services within schools. Additionally, this study will provide valuable insights for other researchers interested in exploring this topic further.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To measure the Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Levels Students in terms of their Gender and Locality
2. To measure the Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Levels Students in terms of their Gender and Locality
3. To find out the difference in Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Gender
4. To find out the difference in Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level students in terms of their Locality
5. To find out the difference in Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Gender
6. To find out the difference in Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Locality
7. To find out the relationship between Mental Health and Emotional Adjustment Ability of secondary Level students
8. To find out the relationship between Mental Health and Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level students

5. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

All the hypotheses are formulated in null form based on objectives (3), (4), (5), (5), (6), (7) and (8)

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Gender

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Locality

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Gender

H₀₄: There is no significant difference in Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Locality

H₀₅: There is no significant relationship between Mental Health and Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students

H₀₆: There is no significant relationship between and Mental Health and Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students

6. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Method: The Descriptive Survey Method was used to carry out the present study.

Population and Sample of the Study: In the present study, all students studying in class X within the Cooch Behar district under the West Bengal Board of Secondary Education (WBBSE) were considered as the population. For sample selection, the researchers used a combination of convenience and simple random sampling technique to select eight (8) schools, comprising four urban and four rural high schools as well as 160 secondary level school students. Initially, convenience sampling was used to identify and choose the schools. Subsequently, the researchers selected 160 students (80 boys and 80 girls) using simple random sampling technique. From each school, 10 boys and 10 girls were selected for the study.

7. TOOLS OF THE STUDY USED

The following tools were used to carry out the present study

- Adjustment Inventory:** The Adjustment Inventory for School Students (AISS), developed by A.K.P. Sinha and R.P.Singh (2005) was applied to assess the adjustment of secondary level students in two areas namely Emotional and

Educational Adjustment. The inventory comprised 60 items for three areas of adjustment, namely Emotional, Social and Educational. The reliability of the inventory was determined by split-half method (93), test-retest method (94), and K-R formula-20 (93).

- Mental Health Scale:** Mental Health scale by Sushma Talesara and Akhtar Bano was used for the present study. This scale consist 54 items. The scale is categorized into five dimensions: (i) Schools related causes (ii) Home related causes, (iii) Peer group related causes, each dimension encompassing a specific number of items. Reliability of the scale was determined by Split-half method and value of reliability is 0.72.

8 RESULT AND INTERPRETATION

Analysis and interpretation of data for the 1st objective

- To measure the Emotional Adjustment Ability levels of Secondary Level students in terms of their Gender and Locality

Table 1: Emotional Adjustment Ability Levels of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Gender and Locality

Levels of Emotional Adjustment Ability	Range of Z Scores	Gender		Locality	
		Boys	Girls	Rural	Urban
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Extremely Unsatisfactory	+2.01 & above	3 (3.75%)	4 (5%)	2 (2.5%)	5 (6.25%)
Unsatisfactory	+1.26 to +2.00	5 (6.25 %)	7 (8.75%)	7(8.75%)	5 (6.25%)
Below Average	+0.51 to +1.25	12 (15%)	13 (16.25%)	14 (17.5%)	11 (13.75%)
Average	-0.50 to +0.50	38 (47.75%)	34 (42.5%)	41(51.25%)	39 (48.75%)
Above Average	-0.1.25 to -0.51	14 (17.5%)	15 (18.75%)	17 (21.25%)	12 (15%)
High	-2.00 to -1.26	8 (10 %)	6 (7.5%)	7 (8.75%)	7 (8.75%)
Extremely High	-2.01 & below	0 (0%)	1 (1.25%)	0(0%)	1 (1.25%)

Figure 1: Graphical Presentation of Emotional Adjustment Ability Levels of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Gender and Locality

Interpretation: The data in the table-1 shows the emotional adjustment ability of secondary level students, differentiated by gender and locality. A significant proportion of students, 47.75% of boys and 42.5% of girls, fall into the average adjustment category, indicating a baseline level of emotional health among this demographic. Girls show a higher tendency towards extremely unsatisfactory (5%) and unsatisfactory (8.75%) adjustments compared to boys (3.75% and 6.25%, respectively), indicating that girls may face greater emotional challenges. In terms of locality, urban students exhibit a higher average adjustment rate (48.75%) than their rural peers (41.25%), indicating that urban environments might provide more supportive conditions for emotional well-being. Conversely, rural students show a higher incidence of below-average adjustment (17.5%) compared to urban students (13.75%). Overall, these findings highlight the importance of considering both gender and locality when addressing emotional adjustment needs, pointing to the necessity for targeted interventions to support students, particularly those in rural areas and female students facing emotional difficulties.

Analysis and interpretation of data for the 2nd objective

- To measure the Educational Adjustment Ability levels of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Gender and Locality

Table 2: Educational Adjustment Ability Levels of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Gender and Locality

Levels of Educational Adjustment Ability	Range of Z scores	Gender		Locality	
		Boys	Girls	Rural	Urban
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Extremely Unsatisfactory	+2.01 & above	4 (5%)	3 (3.75%)	2(2.25%)	5(6.25%)
Unsatisfactory	+1.26 to +2.00	4 (5%)	7 (8.75%)	5 (6.25%)	6 (7.5%)
Below Average	+0.51 to +1.25	12 (15%)	12 (15%)	11(13.75%)	13(16.25%)
Average	-0.50 to +0.50	40 (50%)	38 (47.5%)	37(46.25%)	41(51.25%)
Above Average	-0.51 to -1.25	15 (18.75%)	14 (17.5%)	17(21.25%)	12(15%)
High	-1.26 to -2.00	3 (3.75%)	5 (6.25%)	6 (7.5%)	2(2.25%)
Extremely High	-2.01 & below	2 (2.5%)	1 (1.25%)	2 (2.5%)	1 (1.25%)

Figure-2: Graphical Presentation of Educational Adjustment Ability Levels of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Gender and Locality

Interpretation: The data in the table-2 shows the educational adjustment abilities of secondary level students, categorized by gender and locality. A substantial majority of students, 50% of boys and 47.5% of girls, demonstrate average level educational adjustment, highlighting a strong foundational performance across genders. However, a greater proportion of girls (8.75%) fall into the unsatisfactory category compared to boys (5%), suggesting potential challenges in educational engagement among female students. In terms of locality, urban students show a slightly higher average adjustment rate (51.25%) compared to rural students (46.25%), indicating that urban environments may better support educational achievement. Conversely, rural students exhibit a higher percentage in the above-average category (21.25%) compared to their urban counterparts (15%). The data reveals a complex interaction between gender and locality, emphasizing the need for tailored educational strategies to address the specific challenges faced by rural students and girls, thereby enhancing overall educational adjustment and success.

Analysis and interpretation of data for the 3rd objective and 1st hypothesis

- **Objective 3 :** To find out the difference in Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level students in terms of their Gender
- **H₀₁:** There is no significant difference in Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level students in terms of their Gender

Table 3: Comparison of Emotional Adjustment Ability between Boys and Girls Secondary Level Students

Gender	N	M	SD	DF	Observed t- Value	Critical Value	t-	Remarks at 5% Level
Boys	80	8.66	3.64	158	0.62	1.97		Not Significant
Girls	80	8.32	3.19					

Interpretation: The table-3 shows a comparison of emotional adjustment abilities between secondary level boys and girls, revealing a sample of 80 students for each gender. The mean (M) emotional adjustment score for boys is 8.66 with a standard deviation (SD) of 3.64, while girls have a mean score of 8.32 and a standard deviation of 3.19. The calculated t-value is 0.62, which is lower than the critical t-value of 1.97 at a 5% significance level, indicating that the difference in emotional adjustment ability between boys and girls is not statistically significant. This indicates that, in this sample, gender does not appear to have a meaningful impact on emotional adjustment among secondary level students.

Analysis and interpretation of data for the 4th objective and 2nd hypothesis

- **Objective 4 :** To find out the difference in Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Locality
- **H₀₂:** There is no significance difference in Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students in terms of their Locality

Table 4 : Comparison of Emotional Adjustment Ability between Rural and Urban Secondary Level Students

Locality	N	M	SD	DF	Observed t-Value	Critical t-Value	Remarks at 5% Level
Rural	80	8.5	3.33	158	0.019	1.97	Not Significant
Urban	80	8.49	3.53				

Interpretation: The table-4 compares the emotional adjustment abilities of secondary level students from rural and urban localities, with both groups consisting of 80 students. The mean (M) score for rural students is 8.5, with a standard deviation (SD) of 3.33, while urban students have a mean score of 8.49 and a standard deviation of 3.53. The observed t-value is 0.019, which is significantly lower than the critical t- value of 1.97 at a 5% significance level, indicating that the difference in emotional adjustment ability between students from rural and urban backgrounds is not statistically significant. This suggests that locality does not play a substantial role in affecting the emotional adjustment capabilities of secondary level students in this sample.

Analysis and interpretation of data for the 5th objective and 3rd hypothesis

- **Objective 5 :** To find out the difference in the Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level students in terms of their Gender
- **H₀₃:** There is no significant difference in the Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level students in terms of their Gender

Table 5: Comparison of Educational Adjustment Ability between Boys and Girls Secondary Level Students

Gender	N	M	SD	DF	Observed t-Value	Critical t-Value	Remarks at 5% Level
Boys	80	12.83	4.40	158	0.26	1.97	Not Significant
Girls	60	12.67	3.25				

Interpretation: The table -5 shows a comparison of educational adjustment abilities between secondary level boys and girls students. The sample consists of 80 boys with a mean (M) score of 12.83 and a standard deviation (SD) of 4.40, while 60 girls have a mean score of 12.67 with a standard deviation of 3.25. The observed t- value is 0.26, which is considerably lower than the critical t- value of 1.97 at a 5% significance level, indicating that the difference in educational adjustment ability between boys and girls is not statistically significant. This suggests that gender does not have a meaningful impact on educational adjustment among secondary level students in this sample.

Analysis and interpretation of data for the 6th objective and 4th hypothesis

- **Objective 6:** To find out the difference in the Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level students in terms of their Locality
- **H₀₄:** There is no significance difference in the Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level students in terms of their Locality

Table 6: Comparison of Educational Adjustment Ability between Rural and Urban Secondary Level Students

Locality	N	M	SD	DF	Observed t-Value	Critical t-Value	Remarks at 5% Level
Rural	80	11.92	3.18	158	2.63	1.97	Significant
Urban	80	13.58	4.28				

Interpretation: The table -6 compares the educational adjustment abilities of secondary level students based on locality, with both rural and urban groups consisting of 80 students each. Rural students have a mean (M) score of 11.92 and a standard deviation (SD) of 3.18, while urban students show a higher mean score of 13.58 with a standard deviation of 4.28. The observed t- value is 2.63, which exceeds the critical t- value of 1.97 at a 5% significance level, indicating a statistically significant difference in educational adjustment abilities between rural and urban students. This suggests that locality has a meaningful impact on the educational adjustment capabilities of secondary level students, with urban students demonstrating better adjustment than their rural counterparts.

Analysis and interpretation of data for the 7th objective and 5th hypothesis

- **Objective 7:** To find out the relationship between Mental Health and Emotional Adjustment Ability of secondary Level students
- **H₀₅:** There is no significant relationship between Mental Health and Emotional Adjustment Ability of the Secondary Level Students

Table 7: Correlation Coefficient between Mental Health and Emotional Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students

N	ΣX	ΣY	ΣX^2	ΣY^2	ΣXY	r (Correlation Coefficient)	P-Value	Remarks at 5% Level
160	26303	1353	4403939	13153	224779	0.201323	0.138	Significant

*X= Mental Health, *Y=Emotional Adjustment Ability

Interpretation: Table-7 presents the correlation coefficient between emotional adjustment ability and mental health, based on a sample of 160 secondary level students. The observed correlation coefficient ($r=0.201323$) indicates a positive relationship between mental health (X) and emotional adjustment ability (Y). This correlation is statistically significant since the value of the correlation coefficient exceeds the P-value at the 0.05 significance level. This suggests that as students' emotional adjustment improves, their mental health is positively correlated with it. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which posits no relationship between mental health and emotional adjustment ability, is rejected.

Analysis and interpretation of data for the 8th objective and 6th hypothesis

- **Objective 8:** To find out the relationship between Mental Health and Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level students

- **H₀₆:** There is no significant relationship between Mental Health and Educational Adjustment Ability of the Secondary Level students

Table 8: Correlation Coefficient between Mental Health and Educational Adjustment Ability of Secondary Level Students

N	ΣX	ΣY	ΣX^2	ΣY^2	ΣXY	r(Correlation Coefficient)	P-Value	Remarks at 5% Level
160	26303	2041	4403939	28403	333586	-0.14118	0.138	Significant

*X= Mental Health, *Y= Educational Adjustment Ability

Interpretation: Table-8 shows the correlation coefficient between educational adjustment ability and mental health, based on a sample of 160 secondary level students. The correlation coefficient ($r=-0.14118$) indicates a slight negative relationship between mental health (X) and educational adjustment ability (Y). Since the absolute value of the correlation coefficient $r=0.14118$ is greater than the P-Value of 0.138, the correlation is statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level. This means that there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, which suggests no relationship between the two variables. Thus, while the correlation is weak, it is still statistically significant, indicating that the two variables are related, although the relationship is negative and weak.

Major Findings:

- In the context of emotional adjustment ability, a significant proportion of students, 47.75% of boys and 42.5% of girls, fall into the average adjustment category, indicating a baseline level of emotional health among this demographic. In terms of locality, urban students exhibit a higher average adjustment rate (48.75%) than their rural peers (41.25%), indicating that urban environments might provide more supportive conditions for emotional well-being. However, no significant difference was found in emotional adjustment ability based on gender and locality of secondary level students.
- In the context of educational adjustment, a substantial majority of students, 50% of boys and 47.5% of girls, showed average educational adjustment, highlighting a strong foundational performance across genders. In terms of locality, urban students showed a slightly higher average adjustment rate (51.25%) compared to rural students (46.25%), indicating that urban environments may better support educational achievement. However, no significant difference was found in emotional adjustment ability and mental health based on gender of secondary level students. But, a significant difference was found in emotional adjustment ability based on locality.
- A positive correlation was found between emotional adjustment and mental health of secondary level students in this study. However, a slight negative correlation was observed between educational adjustment and mental health of students.

9. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Every individual seeks to fulfil their basic physical needs, such as hunger and thirst, as well as to ensure their safety and

protect themselves from harm. These fundamental needs are essential for survival and play a critical role in an individual's overall well-being. When a person is unable to adjust to their environment, whether due to social, emotional, or physical challenges, it can hinder their ability to develop a healthy and well-rounded personality. According to table- 1 regarding the level of emotional adjustment it's clear that most of the students fall into average level of emotional adjustment category. In terms of gender, 38 boys (nearly 50%) and 34 (42.5%) fall in this category. And around 20% boys and 24% girls falls between below average to extremely unsatisfactory level. Additionally; urban students exhibited a higher average level of emotional adjustment compared to their rural counterparts. These findings suggest that some students are facing emotional adjustment challenges. Therefore, it is crucial for the government, teachers, educators, and parents to pay attention to these issues and support the emotional adjustment of students to foster their overall well-being and development. Table 2 reveals that 40 boys (50%) and 38 girls (47.5%) fall into the average level of educational adjustment. Additionally, 20% of boys and 22% of girls are categorized between below average to extremely unsatisfactory levels. When considering locality, 41(51.25%) urban students and 37(46.25%) rural students also demonstrate average levels of adjustment. However, it is important to note that some students face educational adjustment challenges. It is crucial for teachers and parents to address these issues and provide the necessary support, enabling students to better adjust to their educational environments. Table 3 demonstrates that the difference in emotional adjustment abilities between boys and girls is not statistically significant. This finding suggests that gender does not have a meaningful impact on educational adjustment among secondary level students in this sample. This result aligns with previous studies, such as Shinde (2018), who found no significant gender differences in emotional adjustment, and Murgan (2017), who reported no gender differences in overall adjustment. Table -4 illustrates the differences in emotional adjustment between urban and rural students are not statistically significant. The findings suggest that locality does not significantly affect the emotional adjustment capabilities of secondary level students in this sample. This result is consistent with the study conducted by Jadhav (2016), which also found no substantial impact of locality on emotional adjustment. Table -5 indicates that the differences in educational adjustment between boys and girls are not statistically significant. This finding aligns with the study by Ralte et al. (2023), which also reported no significant differences between boys and girls in emotional adjustment. Table 6 reveals a statistically significant difference between urban and rural students, indicating that locality affects educational adjustment in this sample. This result aligns with the study conducted by Bajaj & Kaur (2020), who also found differences in educational adjustment between urban and rural students. Table 7 shows a slight positive correlation between emotional adjustment and mental health. This finding is similar to the results of Minchekar & Mangore (2019), who also found a positive relationship between mental health and emotional adjustment. Table 8 reveals a slight negative correlation between mental health and educational adjustment, indicating that improved mental health does not always lead to better educational outcomes. However, further research is necessary to explore the complexities of this relationship and identify effective interventions that support both mental health and educational adjustment ability.

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